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A Study of Risk and Return Analysis with Selected Securities of National Stock Exchange

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Abstract: The main objective of this study is to analyze the risk and return characteristics of selected securities listed on the National Stock Exchange of India (NSE). The study aims to provide investors with a clear understanding of how different securities perform in terms of returns and the level of risk associated with them. By examining historical price data, the research evaluates average returns, variability, and systematic risk using appropriate financial tools and techniques. The Indian stock market has witnessed significant growth and transformation in recent years, offering a wide range of investment opportunities. In this context, understanding the relationship between risk and return becomes essential for making informed investment decisions. This study highlights how diversification across selected securities can help investors optimize returns while minimizing risk.

Keywords: Risk, Return, NSE, Securities, Portfolio, Investment Analysis.

1. Introduction

Stock market is one of the vital indicators for economic development in a country. Different companies stocks use to trade in the stock market which involves both risk and return. The investors invest in the stock market with an expected return in the future. The actual returns of different stocks differ from expected return due to volatility in the stock market. When the volatility of the stock market is high the risk involves in the investment goes high. There is no fixed return and risk in the stock market. So, trading in stock market is very risky for investors. It requires proper analysis of risk and return. So, in the competitive world researchers are also doing the analysis of volatile stock market. This research will be help for investors to get more return from their investment. Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and National Stock exchange (NSE) are the two most important stock exchanges in Indian stock market. In the field of finance risk and return are two fundamental concepts that the that guide investment decisions. returns are refer the

to the gain or loss earned on an investment over a particular period, while risk represents the uncertainty associated with achieving the expected returns. Investors generally expected higher returns for the taking the higher risk. Therefore, understanding the relationship between risk and returns is essential for the making rational and informed investment choices in the securities of the market.

1.1. Meaning of Risk

Risk is the uncertainty regarding the outcomes of an event or decision, representing the potential for the negative consequence and the positive opportunities. Risk is the potential for loss or the unpredictability of how a choice or action till turnout. Risk can be caused by a number of things and the actual returns deviated from the project returns and the lead to cash invested. Risk is measure of uncertainty or volatility of an investment returns and it can arise from various sources such as market fluctuation, credit defaults or interest changes.

1.2. Return

Return refers to the benefit, profit, or gain that an investor receives from an investment over a specific period of time. It shows how much the investment has grown or earned, helping investors evaluate whether the investment is profitable or not. Return is an essential concept in finance because it helps compare different investment options and measure the performance of stocks, bonds, mutual funds, and other assets.

2. Literature Survey

2.1. Sushma K. S., Charithra C. M. & Dr. Bhavya Vikas (2019)

In their study of selected financial services companies listed on the NSE, the authors employed statistical tools such as beta, standard deviation, covariance, and correlation to examine risk and return. They analysed monthly closing prices for eight companies, comparing their risk profiles before and after significant market events like demonetization. Their findings reveal significant differences in returns among companies, indicating varied volatility levels and the influence of macroeconomic events on investor risk perception. This study reinforces that diversified risk assessment techniques help investors make informed decisions in dynamic market conditions.

2.2. N. Lalitha (2025)

N. Lalitha investigated the risk–return relationship for stocks traded on the NSE using the CAPM model. By constructing portfolios based on beta values over a long period (2006–2023), the study concluded that traditional beta did not always show a statistically significant positive relationship with expected returns. This outcome suggests that relying solely on beta may not fully capture return expectations, especially during periods with unusual market conditions such as financial reforms or crises. It highlights the importance of incorporating additional risk measures for accurate return prediction

2.3. P Subramanyam, Nalla Balla Kalyan, (2018)

Numerous assets from the Indian ordinary marketplace are examined in this study. Investors can choose which securities to purchase by carefully weighing risk and return. It provides information on the risk and reward performance of various market stocks. The historical data can be used to monitor the trends that the scripts are adhering to. The link between scrip prices and market fluctuations is the main subject of this study. Despite the fact that it might be difficult to spot patterns in price movements, both technical and fundamental analysis have been used.

3. Statement of the Problem

The investors are majority in investing in securities involves a trade-off where risk and returns are uncertain, due to the uncertainty of returns of the stock market, making it difficult to predict future returns, which are linked to the inherent risk of

the security.to evaluate the mean returns of stocks and identify the stocks with high returns.

3.1. Needs of the Study

Due to a lack of knowledge, investors are generally risk-averse and require higher expected returns to compensate for higher risk. Analysing the securities helps identify the efficient frontier where an investor can achieve the best possible returns for a given level of risk. Investors invest in the stock market despite its being a good source of capital.

3.2. Objectives of the Study

- To study the fluctuation in share prices of selected companies.
- To comparative of risk and return of the companies.
- To study the risk involved in the selected securities of the company.
- To make rank of the companies of risk and returns.

3.3. Scope of the Study

One of the main specialties involved in controlling industrial hazards is return and risk analysis. Even return and risk analysis has become a contentious topic. Return and risk analysis assists investors in making judgments about their investments and in diversifying their holdings to safeguard their capital

4. Data Collection

Secondary data is already existing data collected from www.nseindia.com,journals,reference book.The present study is an analytical approach. It is used to describe the investor’s investment pattern details. It involved calculating the risk and return of selected securities of the selected 6 companies during the 3 years

Average rate of return

$$= \frac{\text{closing stock} - \text{opening stock}}{\text{opening stock}} \times 100 \tag{1}$$

Beta Formula

$$n \sum xy - \sum x \sum \frac{y}{n} \sum x^2 - \sum x^2 \tag{2}$$

$$\text{Variance} = \sqrt{SD} \tag{3}$$

$$\text{Standard DEviation} = \sqrt{(R - R\bar{R})^2} \tag{4}$$

5. Data Analysis

Table 1: Calculation of return for the year 2023

COMPANIES	RETURN
RELIANCE INFRASTRUC-TURE	70.705
ICICI BANK	747.6075
HDFC BANK	674.5625
WIPRO LIMITED	95.945
KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK	269.7525
TOTAL AVERAGE	371.7145

Figure 1: Calculation of return for the year 2023.

Figure 3: Calculation of return for the year 2025.

The table 4.1 and graph shows the company returns. ICICI BANK had a highest return (747.6075), while compared with the lowest return of reliance infrastructure (70.705). the average return was 371.7145 with wide high returns of the banks.

The table4.3 and graph show the returns of the five companies ICICI BANK performed with the highest returns (1373.486) and compared with the other companies. HDFC BANK shows the moderate return (863.573) Kotak Mahindra bank shows the stable (321.0733) and the reliance (158.383) and Wipro (158.936) companies shows the lowest performances.

Table 2: Calculation of return for the year 2024

COMPANIES	RETURN
RELIANCE INFRASTRUC-TURE	139.517
ICICI BANK	1079.190
HDFC BANK	714.026
WIPRO LIMITED	151.5291
KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK	269.7525
TOTAL AVERAGE	470.8029

Table 4: Calculation of risk for the year 2023

COMPANIE	RETURN	AVERAGE	R-R	R ²
Reliance Infrast-structure	70.705	371.7145	-301.0095	90,606.7190
ICIC BANK	747.6075	371.7145	375.893	141,295.5474
HDFC BANK	674.5625	371.7145	302.848	91,716.9111
KOTAK MAHIN-DRA BANK	269.7525	371.7145	-101.962	10,396.2494
	371.7145			3,94,418.074

Figure 2: Calculation of return for the year 2024.

Figure 4: Calculation of risk for the year 2023.

The table 4.2 and the graph indicates the company return. The ICICI BANK can be performed the highest return (1079.190) and the reliance (139.517) and Wipro companies (151.5291) can be performed the lowest returns.

The table 4.4 and the graph show the returns of the five companies ICICI BANK performed with the highest returns and compared with the other companies. HDFC BANK shows a moderate return, Kotak Mahindra Bank shows a stable return, and Wipro shows the lowest performance.

Table 3: Calculation of return for the year 2025

COMPANIES	RETURN
RELIANCE INFRASTRUC-TURE	158.383
ICICI BANK	1373.486
HDFC BANK	863.573
WIPRO LIMITED	158.936
KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK	321.0733
TOTAL AVERAGE	575.09026

Table 5: Calculation of risk for the year 2024.

COMPANIE	RETURN	AVERAGE	R-R	$\sqrt{\frac{\sum (R-R)^2}{n}}$
RELIANCE INFRASTRUCTURE	139.517	470.8029	-331.2859	109,750.348
ICICI BANK	1079.190	470.8029	608.3871	370,134.863
HDFC BANK	714.026	470.8029	243.2231	59,157.48
WIPRO LIMITED	151.5291	470.8029	-319.8029	102,273.89
KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK	269.7525	470.8029	-201.0504	40,421.263
	470.8029			6,81,737.844

Figure 5: Calculation of risk for the year 2024.

The table 4.5 and graph shows the interpretation of the risk analysis for 2024. ICICI BANK shows the highest risk due to large return fluctuations. And other companies of reliance infrastructure and Wipro Ltd and HDFC BANK has moderated the low risk and fell below the expected return.

Table 6: Calculation of risk for the year 2025.

COMPANIE	RETURNS	AVERAGE	R-R	$\sqrt{\frac{\sum (R-R)^2}{n}}$
RELIANCE INFRASTRUCTURES	158.383	575.09026	-416.70726	173,644.941
ICICI BANK	1373.486	575.09026	798.39574	637,435.758
HDFC BANK	863.573	575.09026	288.48274	83,222.291
WIPRO LIMITED	158.936	575.09026	-416.15426	173,184.368
KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK	321.0733	575.09026	-254.01696	64,524.616
	575.09026			11,32,011.97

Figure 6: Calculation of risk for the year 2025.

The table 4.6 and the graph indicate the data indicates the ICICIBANK has the highest risk and the other companies of reliance and Wipro companies have stable returns, and HDFC BANK and KOTAKMAHINDRA BANK have the lowest return.

Table 7: Comparison between ICICI BANK and KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK .

COMPANIES	STANDARD DEVIATION	VARIANCE
ICICI BANK	98,046.83	313.16
KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK	877.94	29.63

Figure 7: Comparison between ICICI BANK and KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK .

The table and graph included ICICI BANK which shows the significantly higher standard deviation (98,046.83) and variance (313.16) is more risky and volatile compared to KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK which has a standard deviation (877.94) and variance (29.63) and is more stable and predictable return.

Table 8: Calculation of beta for five companies.

COMPANIE	MARKET PRICE(X)	STOCK RETURN(Y)	X ²	XY
RELIANCE INFRASTRUCTURE	74.19	73.50	5,504.161	5,452.965
ICICI BANK	1,258.240	1259.70	1,583,167.898	1,585,004.93
HDFC BANK	782.3	780.10	611,993.29	6,10,272.23
WIPRO LIMITED	189.05	197.58	35,739.903	37,352.499
KOTAK MAHINDRA BANK	371.10	370.40	137,715.21	1,37,455.44
	1,892.58	2,681.28	38,078,283.6	2,370,631.064

Figure 8: Calculation of beta for five companies.

The beta slope of the representative regression line. Beta described the relationship between market price and stock return. Beta values show the consistent upward pattern with high market price with high returns of ICICI BANK and HDFC BANK while other companies of reliance and Wipro show the stable stock returns and less effected market changes.

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